

www.arseam.com

Impact Factor: 1.13

LEVERAGING BRANDING THROUGH SOCIAL MEDIA: A STUDY ON MARKETING PROFESSIONALS

Madhusmita Choudhury

Asst. Prof. Affinity Business School, Odisha, India

ABSTRACT

In the era of internet, digitisation & social Media, Sales & Marketing is no longer a different entity hence; marketing professionals need to learn how to shape of information about themselves, their companies & their products. It is a new revolution in the era of web 2.0 & Social media the way company & their customer communicate. In fact social media act as a bicycle with seats for customers & pedals for two riders i.e. Sales & Marketing, one behind the other. With the changing techniques of buyers, sales must respond with practices which meet the buying needs. Social Media have allowed people to build communities as large as it can be by making the world smaller in this process. Blogospheres has tremendously changed the medium business talks to each other, their customers, their stakeholders, their employees & the media by impacting on sales. The sales & marketing components of business feel the impact of this revolution more intensely than in any other sector. Companies are changing their sales strategy by replacing it with the emerging & advent new technologies of social media. The present study highlight a new approach which incorporates social media to became “*Smarketing*” & overhauling the complete company culture in the line of sales & marketing by social selling.

Purpose of the study: To Find out the Customer’s opinion for the companies to be in the Social media. This study aims to find out most reliable company strategy for creating trust factor through the use of Social Media. It also aims to find out the impact of social media which creates an attitude to purchase.

Approach used: Pragmatic Approach

Methodology used: Data Collection from both primary & secondary sources with due application of suitable statistical techniques.

Type of Research Paper: Research Paper

Keywords : Social Media, Sales, Promotional strategy, customer perception, consumer satisfaction

INTRODUCTION

Today people collect lot of information about any company & about their product from the internet or from the web 2.0 technologies; hence it became essential to tap sales with social media which may act as a arm of the sales professionals with lots of information what customer thinks along with the prospects by eliminating the imbalance of information. According to Mr. Marc Perramond, product manager, “We recognise the tremendous growth of the social media & realized we wanted leverage that growth in sales & marketing, all the companies sales professional use Linked in & Twitter to participate in this type of conversation”. Perramond suggests that sales professional can use Twitter to establish their own brand in the company. They can make mini-blog to connect customers as well as company. He further suggested the sales professionals to be the biggest part of the growing oceans of information with the new & ever changing technology to became more productive. There are many Business to Business Companies who helps sales professional to increase their sales productivity. Since 2007, web 2.0 & social media strategically helps the companies to leverage their sales & marketing. Marketing has adopted a new media because of the multi dimensional mentality of the people. Now-a-days sales department has used the media because of the relationship network that exist in social media. Company like INSIDE VIEW recruits sales professional to leveraging the sales growth of their product by tapping social media by boasting a 410 percent of increase in sales growth from 2007 to 2008 since its inception by making its mission to maximize its growth with the advantages by changing traditional media with social media. The employees of INSIDEVIEW are well connected with Linked in, which broadens the company’s overall base of contacts.

In the past, sales pushed products onto customers by assuming that the company knew what was good for the customers. Social media helps companies to make a well balance of consultative selling (selling that consults with customers to uncover customer needs) & Relationship Selling (creating a strong relationship before pushing the products onto customers). Combining both the selling techniques with the tools of social media create a new horizon for sales, which is driven by the new set of buyers. Business Leaders must recognize that now-a-days sales is much more than, simply updating existing customer relationship management systems. It can be leveraged by adopting new technologies with social media by slapping outdated process. Social media helps sales professionals to interact with customer N times a day by getting immediate response.

Percent of People Who Use Social Networks	Percent Yes
<i>Do you ever use / have a profile on... (Poll Taken in early 2012)</i>	
Any social network	56 %
Facebook	54 %
LinkedIn	13 %
Twitter	10 %
Google+	8 %

<http://www.statisticbrain.com/social-networking-statistics/> date verified on 21.11.2012

Social Media provides a platform to develop a community for connecting like-minded people to network for work related experiences, issues & for sharing problems. It provides a platform for the companies to get the remarks of the customer & prospects about their problems on various products/services offered by companies along with the tentative solutions too. It also provides a platform to disseminate information across globe. Social selling is a sales technique that leverages social media, to get & maintain a 360 degree picture of the clients & their influencer on an ongoing basis. It allows salespeople to manage & maintain five times as many active customers compared to traditional techniques. [3]

The value building figure of social media Ref-4

The most effective means for buying has always been by word-of-mouth. Now it can be leveraged with many followers in Twitters & maximum likes in Facebook. This will be word-of-mouth at its best. Thousands of potential prospects can get the information about the products at the cost of nothing. Word-of-mouth & engagement have always been the most effective ways to sell products/concepts/opinion/people. President Barak Obama’s presidential team integrated social media with all forms of media to achieve success by challenging the traditional ways by creating a supporter with over 13 million people on an e-mail list as well as 5 million people connected as friends on social network sites which includes 3 million in Facebook alone. These million of friends made Barak Obama a rock star

amongst the people by creating a political evolution in 2008. The same strategy can be applied within the archaic of Sales too.

Sales can be leveraged through Linked In

Linked in is one of the world's largest professional networking sites with more than 120 million members in over 200 countries & territories. [2] Linked In users are key decision makers, have high personal incomes and who understand the power & value of Social networking. Through Linked In Sales professional opens the door of connections by identifying top level executives without getting the way of bottom line employee. It also helps leveraging the sales through some unique features like *professional network* (where a sales professional can highlight their professional skills which would act like a resume), *Linked in groups* (which gives an opportunity to interact with business professionals on a deeper level by posting blogs, responding to discussions, directly contacting members, inviting members to connect with you, posting news & events and by actively participating in groups specifically related to business focus increases visibility within Linked in networks by letting an expert in the field) *Linked In Search* (by providing the sales professional the

<http://theundercoverrecruiter.com/infographic-linkedin-user-statistics-network-profiles-groups-applications/>

ability to search companies, jobs, and answers to questions as wells as allied mind people, which enables a competitive advantage over others) *advanced search on Linked* (one of the most valuable lead- generations features on the network), *Questions & answers* (a powerful place to show knowledge & for becoming an expert in the area), *Recommendations* (by creating powerful image in the eyes of potential customer through peer recommendations & testimonials- [to get a 100% profile completion status, Linked In requires a minimum 3

peoples recommendations which should be credible & authentic]) and *blog posts* (by enabling a sales professional blog much broader visibility across the Linked in network)

Sales can be leveraged through Twitter

The advantages of sales professional to use it is, they can get the answer instantly & can bounce back with ideas to those people, whom they can ever met. It can be used in *monitoring function* (it enables us to monitor what is being said about companies product & services along with the competition details) , *Build a large base of followers* (which enables the sales professional to access many more people quickly), *exposure to company products, Brand yourself, Micro blogging* (allows sales professional to share information quickly without need to write maximum , marketing people can write the blog & the sales professional can post the link to that blog on twitter), *twit with a purpose* (it enables one to call to action, use the key words to search company & their products and services, to catch the attention of the followers), *time sensitive* (unread twits will disappear in least time), *respond people in 3 ways* (the @ symbol is used to respond directly to someone’s tweet which will be visible globally, sales professional can re-twit immediately and DM[direct & Private message] can create a strong relationship to arrange any professional schedules)

Twitter Company Statistics	Data
Total number of active registered Twitter users	554,750,000
Number of new Twitter users signing up everyday	135,000
Number of unique Twitter site visitors every month	190 million
Average number of tweets per day	58 million
Number of Twitter search engine queries every day	2.1 billion
Percent of Twitter users who use their phone to tweet	43 %
Percent of tweets that come from third party applicants	60%
Number of people that are employed by Twitter	2,500
Number of active Twitter users every month	115 million
Percent of Twitters who don’t tweet but watch other people tweet	40%
Number of days it takes for 1 billion tweets	5 days
Number of tweets that happen every second	9,100
Twitter Annual Advertising Revenue	Revenue
2013 (Projected)	\$399,500,000
2012	\$259,000,000
2011	\$139,000,000
2010	\$45,000,000

<http://www.statisticbrain.com/twitter-statistics/> date verified on 7-5-2013

Sales can be leveraged through Facebook

Till June 2011 Facebook reaches 750 million users. [6] The sales professional quickly find the company page by simply writing the name of the company in the search bar to network with, they can edit their thumbnail where everyone can see the updates & new feed posts, you can create three walls streams or one wall stream which includes posts by page admin & post by connections, users can post any comment on the wall unless they have liked it, setting a custom view for new visitors, upload videos & photos of products & services via e-mail, can remove unused tabs , sales professional embed links to tabs, SP can change the order of tabs, SP can see the what posts receive the most interactions, SP can promote their product with page tagging,

Rapid growth of Facebook users Ref 5, Page 10

Facebook Statistics	Data
Total number of active Facebook users	900 million
Total number of minutes spent on Facebook each month	700 billion
Percent of all Facebook users who log on in any given day	50 %
Percent of 18-34 year olds who check Facebook when they wake up	48 %
Percent of 18-34 year olds who check Facebook before they get out of bed	28 %
Average number of friends per facebook user	130
Average number of pages, groups, and events a user is connected to	80
Average number of photos uploaded per day	250
Global Facebook Reach Statistics	
Number of languages available on the Facebook site	70
Percent of Facebook users who are outside the United States	75 %
Number of users who helped translate Facebook	300,000

Facebook Platform Statistics	
Average number of aps installed on Facebook each day	20 million
Total number of apps and websites integrated with Facebook	7 million
Facebook Mobile Phone Statistics	
Number of Facebook users who access the site through a mobile device	350 million
Every 20 Minutes on Facebook	
Links shared	1 million
Friends requested	2 million
Messages sent	3 million

<http://www.statisticbrain.com/facebook-statistics/> date verified on 18.5.2013

The Landscape of Social Media Users

	% of internet users who....	The service is especially appealing to ...
Use Any Social Networking Site	67%	Adults ages 18-29, women
Use Facebook	67	Women, adults ages 18-29
Use Twitter	16	Adults ages 18-29, African-Americans, urban residents
Use Pinterest	15	Women, adults under 50, whites, those with some college education
Use Instagram	13	Adults ages 18-29, African-Americans, Latinos, women, urban residents
Use Tumblr	6	Adults ages 18-29

Source: Pew Research Center's Internet & American Life Project Post-Election Survey, November 14 – December 09, 2012. N=1,802 internet users. Interviews were conducted in English and Spanish and on landline and cell phones. Margin of error is +/- 2.6 percentage points for results based on internet users. Facebook figures are based on Pew Research Center's Internet & American Life Project Omnibus Survey, December 13-16, 2012. Margin of error for Facebook data is +/- 2.9 percentage points for results based on internet users (n=860).

<https://bufferblog-wpengine.netdna-ssl.com/wp-content/uploads/2013/04/landscape-of-users.jpg>

LITERATURE REVIEW

Roberta J. Schultz, Charles H. Schwepker, Jr, David J. Good, (2012) in his study entitled "Social media usage: an investigation of B2B salespeople", find Results support the hypothesized model suggesting that age negatively affects social media usage, while social media norms positively affect it. Social media usage positively affects sales performance. Customer-oriented selling was not found to be positively related to social media usage, but does have a positive effect on sales performance.

Arthur Meidan, (1980) "Salesforce Management", Management Decision, find A large number of variables influence the approach of the marketing function to the problem of selling, including the state of technology, the economic environment, the social structure, the

climate of the age (political, institutional, religious and educational), available communication media, skills which managers apply and so on. Yet personal selling is by far the major promotional method used to increase profitable sales by offering want satisfactions to markets and customers.

Linnea Hansson, Anton Wrangmo, Klaus Solberg Søylen, (2013) in the study "Optimal ways for companies to use Facebook as a marketing channel", find Most users who have an opinion on the issue accept marketing on Facebook, but only in the right amount. There are basically two groups: those who think that companies have no place on Facebook and those who want companies to be active on Facebook. The latter group emphasizes the importance of meaningful posts without unsolicited sales messages, and would prefer to search for the companies themselves rather than being bombarded by company messages. By far, status updates and pictures/images were found to be the most important functions to respondents.

(2013) "Facebook's increasing level of ad sophistication *Edited by Dennis A. Pitta, University of Baltimore, resulted* The research demonstrates that in terms of click through rates, which associate with awareness, Post Ads and Sponsored Stories generate nearly double the response rate of Social Ads and Web Ads. The probable cause is that post ads often contain some incentive or special offer that prompts action. Since sponsored stories come from users, they are probably more relevant to them than the other forms. Similarly, high click through rates (CTR) equate to lower cost per click (CPC). One consideration is that both the Post Ads and Sponsored Stories are the easiest to track because they drive consumers to specific pages or web sites. The most important element under consideration, effectiveness in promoting purchase, is closely linked to involvement and the report shows that involvement is costly. Sponsored Stories carry the highest cost per thousand (CPM) of the four. Investigating further, the study reports that the click through rates of the three outcomes, range from highest to lowest and cheapest to most expensive as: Post like, to Using an application, to Sharing an application. Presumably, the order is linked to ease. It is easier to post a like than to go through the trouble of installing an application. Similarly, sharing an application requires even more effort. In terms of cost. One lesson is that the most valuable results, sharing applications and installing them carry a higher price than just posting a like. In social media terms, adopting an application forms a bond between the user and an advertiser. For example, an airline's booking application dedicated to frequent fliers, ties the user to that airline. It has the potential of capturing a large amount of share of wallet.

Furthermore, multiplying the effect of an ad through sharing an application with others is even more important.

Edited by **Dennis A. Pitta**, (2012) "Social networks, engagement and potential success", concluded Marketers are just beginning to come to grips with using social marketing for brand promotion and sales. However, it seems that it will be critical to plan and implement strategies that exploit the use of social media not only to make consumers aware of products but to help them engage with the brand and make purchase decisions based on their own wants. Making the process easier by building social momentum will enhance the decision and promises to lead to higher marketing success. It illustrates another old adage, "Make it easy for the customer to buy."

Mervi Vuori, (2012) "Exploring uses of social media in a global corporation" The main uses of social media were identified and conceptualized based on the case company data. Internally, social media was used for internal communication and knowledge transfer, to reach personnel and to conduct internal idea crowd sourcing. Externally, social media was used to enhance communications related to the company brand, to enable dialogue with customers, to build communities with various stakeholder groups and to engage external stakeholders in idea generation via a crowd sourcing platform. A categorization of social media uses for communication, collaboration and connecting vis-à-vis external and internal uses was created. Idea creation practices were further conceptualized as the main enactment of Web 2.0 social media technology.

John S. Hill, Richard R. Still, Ünal O. Boya, in their study "Managing the Multinational Sales Force" find Managing sales forces in multinational contexts is a topic about which little empirical work has been done. This article reports the results of a 14-MNC, 135 subsidiary, survey of multinational sales management practices, focusing in particular on the extent to which head offices influence sales functions in subsidiaries. An industry-by-industry analysis shows that electronic data processing affiliates get considerable head office attention while general consumer goods subsidiaries do not.

Anthony Patino, Dennis A. Pitta, Ralph Quinones, (2012) "Social media's emerging importance in market research", find The market research profession has been affected by developments in social media. First, some of the traditional research methods suffer from changes in consumer communication patterns. As social media supplant communication methods such as telephony and even email, researchers have diminished capacity to reach

consumer subjects. As a result, the social media have spawned a number of research techniques that overcome the problems that have started to affect the old techniques.

Jay M. Bernhardt, Darren Mays, Amanda K. Hall, (2012) "Social marketing at the right place and right time with new media", find The rapid growth of online social networks and near ubiquity of mobile phones in much of the world offers social marketers enormous potential for engaging consumers in radically new ways. The nature of these new communication platforms differs from traditional media in important ways that can make them more effective for marketing, most notably the potential for deeper consumer engagement, multi-directional information exchange, and location-based tracking and messaging.

Seung-A Annie Jin, (2012) "The potential of social media for luxury brand management", find Structural equation modeling (SEM) analyses uncovered dynamic relationships among consumers' perceptions of value-expressive and social-adjustive functions of luxury brands, satisfaction with a luxury brand's (Louis Vuitton) Facebook page, attitudes toward the brand, intentions to utilize the brand's social media (Facebook and Twitter) for online shopping, and intentions to research online and purchase offline (ROPO).

Joel Indrupati, Tara Henari, (2012) "Entrepreneurial success, using online social networking: evaluation", Education, Business and Society, – It is found that social networking is a cheap and easy method of advertising and gives all entrepreneurs a better chance of reaching their target market and, thereby, in succeeding in their ventures.

Jennifer Allyson Dooley, Sandra C. Jones, Don Iverson, (2012) "Web 2.0: an assessment of social marketing principles, find – Results demonstrated that social marketers can employ the following social marketing principles to successfully design and implement a Web 2.0 campaign: consumer orientation, behavior change, market segmentation and targeting, mixed methods, exchange and competition.

John E. Cicala, Rachel K. Smith, Alan J. Bush, (2012) "What makes sales presentations effective – a buyer-seller perspective" uncovers three common themes of an effective sales presentation – knowledge, adaptability, and trust – but exposes a gap between buyer and seller expectations and perspectives of these themes.

Valerie Champoux, Julia Durgee, Lauren McGlynn, (2012) "Corporate Facebook pages: when “fans” attack", find Harm, fear of harm and threatened values are the three basic sources of public outrage. The popularity of social media, particularly Facebook, provides a new venue for unhappy customers to publicly communicate their disdain. By relating to customers on a personal level and planning in advance, companies can recover from Facebook attacks quickly and with minimal damage.

Huaxia Rui, University of Rochester, Simon School of Business, United States , **Yizao Liu,** University of Connecticut, Department of Agricultural and Resource Economics, United States and **Andrew Whinston,** University of Texas at Austin, McCombs School of Business and Department of Economics, United States, in their study “ Whose and what chatter matters? The effect of tweets on movie sales” find Social broadcasting networks such as Twitter in the U.S. and “Weibo” in China are transforming the way online word of mouth (WOM) is disseminated and consumed in the digital age. In the present study, we investigated whether and how Twitter WOM affects movie sales by estimating a dynamic panel data model using publicly available data and well-known machine learning algorithms. We found that chatter on Twitter does matter; however, the magnitude and direction of the effect depend on whom the WOM is from and what the WOM is about. Incorporating the number of followers the author of each WOM message had into our study, we found that the effect of WOM from users followed by more Twitter users is significantly larger than those followed by less Twitter users. In support of some recent findings about the importance of WOM valence on product sales, we also found that positive Twitter WOM is associated with higher movie sales, whereas negative WOM is associated with lower movie sales. Interestingly, we found that the strongest effect on movie sales comes from those tweets in which the authors expressed their intention to watch a certain movie. We attribute this finding to the dual effects of such intention tweets on movie sales: the direct effect through the WOM author's own purchase behavior, and the indirect effect through either the awareness effect or the persuasive effect of the WOM on its recipients. Our findings provide new perspectives to understand the effect of WOM on product sales and have important managerial implications. For example, our study reveals the potential values of monitoring people's intentions and sentiments on Twitter and identifying influential users for companies wishing to harness the power of social broadcasting networks.

Christopher H Purdy, Managing Director, DKT International Turkey, Istanbul, Turkey in his study “Using the Internet and social media to promote condom use in Turkey” find Condoms are an important contraceptive method in Turkey, used by one in three couples using modern methods. However, withdrawal remains the most common form of contraception, resulting in many unwanted pregnancies. To address this issue and increase condom use in Turkey, DKT International, a social marketing enterprise, leveraged the high use of the Internet and social networking to help build Fiesta, a premium condom brand, and promote sales and condom use. By utilising a wide range of digital platforms – a new website, Facebook page, Google Adwords, an e-newsletter, viral marketing, banner ads and involving bloggers – Fiesta achieved strong recognition among the target audience of sexually active young people, though far more men than women. Retail audits, Internet analysis and sales performance suggest that using the Internet was instrumental in establishing Fiesta. Sales reached 4.3 million condoms (of which 8% were sold online) in the first 18 months. In contrast, Kiss, a far more inexpensive DKT condom, launched at the same time but with no digital campaign, sold 2.6 million. With the growing availability and use of the Internet and social media globally, family planning organizations should consider incorporating these technologies into their educational, outreach and marketing programmes

Hiroshi Onishi *Dentsu Inc., Japan* & **Puneet Manchanda** Ross School of Business at the University of Michigan, USA, in their study “Marketing activity, blogging and sales” find The recent growth of consumer-generated media (CGM), also known as “new” media, has changed the interaction between consumers and firms from being unidirectional to being bidirectional. However, CGM are almost always accompanied by traditional media (such as TV advertising). This research addresses the critical question of whether new and traditional media reinforce or damage one another's effectiveness. This question is important because traditional media, in which a manufacturer creates and delivers content to consumers, consume a firm's resources. In contrast to these paid media, new media (in which consumers create content and this content is exchanged between other consumers and potentially between manufacturers) are primarily available for free. This question becomes even more salient when new product launches are involved, as firms typically allocate approximately half of their marketing budgets to support new products. One of the most prevalent forms of new media is blogging. Therefore, we assemble a unique data set from Japan that contains market outcomes (sales) for new products, new media (blogs) and traditional media (TV advertising) in the movie category. We specify a simultaneous equation log-linear system for

market outcomes and the volume of blogs. Our results suggest that new and traditional media act synergistically, that pre-launch TV advertising spurs blogging activity but becomes less effective during the post-launch period and that market outcomes have an effect on blogging quantity. We find detailed support for some of these results via a unique and novel text-mining analysis and replicate our findings for a second product category, cellular phone service. We also discuss the managerial implications of our findings.

Rohayah Kahara, Faizal Yamimib, Ghazali Bunaric, Hadina Habild , Language Academy, Universiti Teknologi Malaysia, Skudai 81310, Malaysia, *Trusting the Social Media in Small Business*, find This study has provided an overview of how Malaysian small business entrepreneurs trust the social media. The study concludes that there are various reasons in using social media by the small business entrepreneurs. Among these, creating networking was favored the most, while other reasons were the least. In terms of level of trust, social media was being trusted moderately by majority of the entrepreneurs. Overall, it can be concluded that social media are still not widely used and trusted among small business entrepreneurs in Malaysia

A. Kazım Kırtış, Filiz Karahan, Çanakkale Onsekiz Mart University Biga FEAS, 17100, Biga Çanakkale, Turkey , Çanakkale Onsekiz Mart University Biga FEAS, 17100, Biga Çanakkale, Turkey, in their study *To Be or Not to Be in Social Media Arena as the Most Cost- Efficient Marketing Strategy after the Global Recession*, find Social media, which starts as a means of entertainment at the first, then became the most recent marketing strategy because of its notable advantages in business field. Social media is used because it has many advantages for time, audience, relations and cost issues. Firms critically need to consider about their businesses and aims then uses the appropriate social media instrument for each of purposes. The communication between firms and their stakeholders on social media is carried out by the firms. Corporate activities rose on social media as well as the number of followers and “likes” increased on corporate social media accounts. As much as firms employ the relevant content, listen and communicate with stakeholders through right route, social media will be mutually effective for firms and customers.

Irem eren erdogmus, marmara university, Anadolu Hissaric campus, Istanbul 34810, Turkey and **Misut Cicek** , Yalova University, Safran Campus, Yalova 77100, Turkey in their study “The impact of social media marketing on brand loyalty” find The results of this study shows that advantageous campaigns on social media are the most significant drivers of brand loyalty

followed by relevancy of the content, popularity of the content among friends, and appearing on different social media platforms and providing applications.

Ioanna Bizirgianni, Panagiota Dionysopoulou, Technological Educational Institute (T.E.I.) of Athens, Ag. *Spyridonos*, Egaleo 12210, Greece. Hellenic Open University, Parodos Aristotelous 18, Patra, 26 335, Greece in their study “The influence of tourist trends of Youth Tourism through Social Media (SM) & Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs)” find The philosophy of social networking based mainly on rapid dissemination of information across the world, with the active participation of users, who have the opportunity to exchange or share an idea, a thought, a message, an opinion in a way of one to many users in real time. This model of communication called on-line oral communication or e-Word of Mouth (e-WOM) and is considered the core for any on-line action or activity. As Qualman [25] says “Word of Mouth goes World of Mouth” as well as that “we have shifted from a world where the information and news was held by a few and distributed to millions, to a world where the information is held by millions and distributed to a few (niche markets)”. In the framework of the extending of social networking, tourism claims its position in internet world through the effort to approach potential travellers in their virtual environment in every way. Since social media concentrate endless information including many useless ones, the tourism industry is invited to make best possible use of this space.

RESEARCH GAP

1. None of the previous literature is talking about Buyers & Sellers Perspective on the use of Social media.
2. None of them as highlighted that social media strategically help leveraging sales.
3. None of them focused that Social media could able to create Trust factor amongst the consumers.
4. None of them highlighted that, which brand category marketing will be leveraged through Social Media.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

- ✓ To find out the Customer’s strongest opinion for the companies to be in the Social media.
- ✓ To find out most reliable company strategy for creating trust factor through the use of Social Media.
- ✓ To find out the factor organisation make their presence in social media.

METHODOLOGY

Keeping the objective in mind the author has collected response only from online through google doc (<https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1kxmilgRWY2QMACUPSA3OXqK1AR318ZBPksVhF32traI/viewform>) from marketing/sales personnel of different companies and also from the professional who directly involve themselves in the branding or selling process to contribute their views online by adopting Non probability- convenience sampling method by using the author's own social media connections. The sample size was determined 5 per variable (Kass & Tinsley, 1979). All the variables were measured & validated through "Content validity " methodology. The research approach is pragmatic in nature. The google form has sent to more than 500 adequate profile to collect response & only 140 responses have collected after filtering the unutilised response. The data collection has started after pre-test from 15 participants to access the content adequacy, including appropriateness of the questions, scales & instruction given. Based on the pre-test feedback the questionnaire was slightly modified to achieve the research objectives. A pilot test has been conducted with 22 responses which include the target sample frame to examine statistical and methodological accuracy which also include the reliability & validity of the scale. The constructs were measured on seven point likert scale, anchored from strongly disagree (1) to strongly agree (7) in interval scale. Respondents were asked to fill the responses the degree to which they believe that they would think the effectiveness of social media for branding.

DATA ANALYSIS & RESULTS

Before the actual data analysis, the final data has been checked to treat the missing values and the author find no missing values (Table 1). The variables were standardised using Z score and the analysis were conducted on the Z value.

Table- 2 explaining the demographic profile of the respondent in this study. Male respondent (91.4%) are dominated over its female counter part (8.6%)only. Highest number of respondent are belonging in the age group of 26-35(51.4%) followed with 18-25 age group (28.6%), 36-45 age group (17.1%) and age group more than 46 (2.9%). Highest number (28.6%) of people from the respondent are solely attached with the strongest social media platform i.e Facebook, 28.5% people are connected with 2 social media platform like (Facebook + Twitter and Linked in + Facebook), 22.9% of people are connected with 3 social

media platform (Linked in , Facebook & Twitter) and 20.1 % of people are connected with more than 3 social media platform.

To find our first objective i.e what is the Customer's strongest opinion for the companies to be in the Social media; the author has run descriptive studies on the 8 variables identified during literature review and found that customers are connected with number of social media to get numerous offers from different companies (Table 3). The author find that companies make their presence in social media platforms to market their product within the target group (5.46) by calculating the mean score (Table-4) which is also got the highest reliability values of .941 (Table-5) which discussed our second objective which is "to find out the most reliable company strategy for creating trust factor through the use of Social Media". To find our 3rd objective is "To find out the factor organisation make their presence in social media" the author did CFA by using AMOS application and the author found that (Figure 1) Social media is basically used to create advert over media marketing, platform to transfer knowledge and is basically a place for new technology. Social media helps in enhance brand image of the products for companies, gives millage to top brand products & creates word of mouth for companies. Companies must learn the techniques of consultative selling, relationship selling & to create trust amongst the target audience. Social media also provide latest updates about product status, offers & discounts to customers. The model is better fit with CFI of .928(Bentler, 1990; Bentler and Bonnet, 1980; Hu and Bentler, 1999) , TLI of .905 (Hu and Bentler, 1999). The convergent validity of all the constructs are highly reliable with the CR >.07 (Hair, J., Black, W., Babin, B., and Anderson, R. (2010) (Table – 7). AVE is a strict & more conservative measure than CR (Malhotra and Dash, 2011, p.702) and the AVE > 0.5 (Table – 7) which explain that the model does not have any convergent validity issues, the variables are correlate well with each other within their parent factor (the latent factor is well explained by its observed variables)

CONCLUSIONS

The companies as well as the Marketing/Sales personnel can leverage Social media to their full extent as people get connected with a company page over SM to stay updated with the numerous offers they extend by targeting people rightly with the right technology. Social media is also used to create advert over media marketing, platform to transfer knowledge and is basically a place for new technology. Social media helps in enhance brand image of the products for companies, gives millage to top brand products & creates word of mouth for

companies. Companies must learn the techniques of consultative selling, relationship selling & to create trust amongst the target audience. Social media also provide latest updates about product status, offers & discounts to customers (Table 3, 4, 5 & Figure 1).

DISCUSSIONS & CONCLUSIONS

The research findings also lack max responses, however if the number of responses could be increased more the research findings & its effect would have been implemented globally.

APPENDIX

Table -1

	Statistics		Mean	Std. Deviation
	Valid	Missing		
Gender	140	0	.09	.281
Age Group	140	0	1.94	.756
Your connectivity with Social Media	140	0	6.31	3.051
SM is a new advent over Media Marketing.	140	0	5.46	1.702
SM creates e-WOM (Word-of-Mouth) essential for any online activity.	140	0	5.00	1.874
SM disseminates information of products/services across globe.	140	0	5.40	1.613
SM is a platform of Knowledge Transfer.	140	0	5.66	1.478
SM is a place of right time, right place with new technology.	140	0	5.31	1.532
SM provides easiest way of information.	140	0	5.54	1.719
SM provides Knowledge of products.	140	0	5.20	1.415
SM creates Positive effect on Sales Performance.	140	0	5.09	1.447
SM enhance brand image of products for companies.	140	0	5.63	1.461
SM gives Mileage to Top Brand products.	140	0	5.43	1.578
SM creates Word-of-Mouth (WOM) for companies.	140	0	5.29	1.326
SM creates Negative effect on Customer Orientation.	140	0	3.51	1.406
SM is a Major Marketing Channel.	140	0	4.63	1.664
SM is a very good platform for companies for Brand Promotion.	140	0	5.60	1.502
SM is an effective platform for customers.	140	0	5.11	1.415
SM can create strong Brand Recognition.	140	0	5.14	1.422
SM is a good platform for crowd sourcing.	140	0	5.09	1.562
SM is a platform of Idea creation.	140	0	4.94	1.554
SM helps in Market Research.	140	0	5.46	1.524
SM engages customers to collect feedback.	140	0	5.43	1.667

SM provides quick customer feedback to companies.	140	0	5.37	1.781
SM enhances Trust for companies.	140	0	4.51	1.524
SM enhance brand image of products for customers.	140	0	5.29	1.547
SM provides updates about product status to customers.	140	0	5.00	1.609
SM creates opportunity for customers to get offers.	140	0	5.37	1.500
SM creates opportunity for customers to get discounts.	140	0	5.06	1.746
SM is an effective platform for companies.	140	0	5.23	1.421
SM provides Multidimensional information.	140	0	5.31	1.532
SM provides a mean for customer to invoke their rage.	140	0	5.06	1.313
SM is a powerful platform where customers can publicly communicate with the companies.	140	0	4.89	1.675
SM provides opportunity for Consultative Selling.	140	0	4.77	1.748
SM provides opportunity for Relationship Selling.	140	0	4.83	1.582
SM is a trusted platform for companies to provide information for their products.	140	0	5.37	1.461
SM enhances Customer Decision to purchase a product.	140	0	5.14	1.520
SM enhances company promises to customer.	140	0	4.74	1.598
SM is a mutually effective platform for customers & companies.	140	0	5.09	1.208
SM can be used for internal communication for the companies.	140	0	4.63	1.813
SM creates network for companies to Market the product.	140	0	5.46	1.579
SM provides opportunities to write blog about products/services for inbound marketing.	140	0	5.26	1.486
SM multifolds companies' communication.	140	0	5.14	1.179
SM can create Brand Loyalty by enhancing its content.	140	0	4.97	1.488
SM provides platform to directly interact with customers.	140	0	5.34	1.608
SM can create WOM (Word-of-Mouth) which enhances intentions for any products to customers.	140	0	4.94	1.334
SM can create WOM (Word-of-Mouth) which enhances sentiments for any products to customers.	140	0	5.11	1.373
SM provides location based tracking of customers.	140	0	4.83	1.803
SM create attitude of customers for a specific	140	0	5.37	1.519

Brand.				
SM is a cheapest way of advertising.	140	0	4.91	2.151
SM can easily reach target market.	140	0	4.63	1.828
SM can enhance behavior of any customer.	140	0	4.60	1.937
SM create Positive WOM (Word-Of-Mouth), leading to Sales.	140	0	5.03	1.618
Educational Background	140	0		

Table – 2

Sample characteristics	Frequency (140)	Percent %
Gender		
Male	128	91.4
Female	12	8.6
Age group		
18-25	40	28.6
26-35	72	51.4
36-45	24	17.1
46 & above	4	2.9
Connectivity with social Media		
Linked In		
Facebook	40	28.6
Twitter	0	0
Others	0	0
None	0	0
Facebook & Twitter	16	11.4
Linked in & Facebook	24	17.1
Lineked in, facebook & twitter	32	22.9
Linked In, Facebook, Twitter, google +	12	8.6
Linked In, Facebook, Twitter, Pintrest, Fiverr	4	2.9
Linked In, Facebook, Twitter, whatsapp	8	5.7
Linked In, Facebook, Twitter, yahoo, g+	4	2.9

Table - 3

Descriptive Statistics			
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
SM creates opportunity for customers to get offers.	140	5.37	1.500
SM provides Multidimensional information.	140	5.31	1.532
SM enhance brand image of products for customers.	140	5.29	1.547
SM is an effective platform for companies.	140	5.23	1.421
SM provides a mean for customer to invoke their rage.	140	5.06	1.313

SM creates opportunity for customers to get discounts.	140	5.06	1.746
SM provides updates about product status to customers.	140	5.00	1.609
SM is a powerful platform where customers can publicly communicate with the companies.	140	4.89	1.675
Valid N (listwise)	140		

Table- 4

Descriptive Statistics			
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
SM creates network for companies to Market the product.	140	5.46	1.579
SM create attitude of customers for a specific Brand.	140	5.37	1.519
SM is a trusted platform for companies to provide information for their products.	140	5.37	1.461
SM provides platform to directly interact with customers.	140	5.34	1.608
SM provides opportunities to write blog about products/services for inbound marketing.	140	5.26	1.486
SM enhances Customer Decision to purchase a product.	140	5.14	1.520
SM multifolds companies' communication.	140	5.14	1.179
SM can create WOM (Word-of-Mouth) which enhances sentiments for any products to customers.	140	5.11	1.373
SM is a mutually effective platform for customers & companies.	140	5.09	1.208
SM create Positive WOM (Word-Of-Mouth), leading to Sales.	140	5.03	1.618
SM can create Brand Loyalty by enhancing its content.	140	4.97	1.488
SM can create WOM (Word-of-Mouth) which enhances intentions for any products to customers.	140	4.94	1.334
SM is a cheapest way of advertising.	140	4.91	2.151
SM provides location based tracking of customers.	140	4.83	1.803
SM provides opportunity for Relationship Selling.	140	4.83	1.582
SM provides opportunity for Consultative Selling.	140	4.77	1.748
SM enhances company promises to customer.	140	4.74	1.598
SM can be used for internal communication for the companies.	140	4.63	1.813
SM can easily reach target market.	140	4.63	1.828
SM can enhance behavior of any customer.	140	4.60	1.937
Valid N (listwise)	140		

Table – 5

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.941	20

Table – 6

CMIN/df	2.333
GFI	.861
AGFI	.792
CFI	.928
TLI	.905

Table – 7

	CR	AVE	MSV	ASV	Cust omer	Aw rns s	Com pany	Stra tegy	Bran ding
	Composite reliability	Average variance extracted	Maximum shared variance	Average shared variance					
	CR > 0.7	AVE > 0.5	MSV < AVE	ASV < AVE					
Cust omer	0.887	0.727	0.228	0.204	0.853				
Aw rns s	0.834	0.627	0.300	0.195	0.448	0.792			
Com pany	0.908	0.768	0.222	0.172	0.424	0.471	0.876		
Stra tegy	0.921	0.795	0.205	0.105	0.453	0.239	0.338	0.892	
Bran ding	0.890	0.730	0.300	0.187	0.478	0.548	0.416	0.213	0.854

No Validity Concerns - Wahoo!

Figure – 1

REFERENCES

1. The New handshake : Sales meet Social Media , By Joan C. Curtis, Barbara Giamance, 2012 ,Greenwood Publishing group, Page IX,X,XI,XII,99,101,104,111,112,113,114 , < http://books.google.co.in/books?id=pcf_C9I7hysC&pg=PA104&dq=leveraging+sales+by++social+media&hl=en&sa=X&ei=L7-bUafdCM6HrgfNmICABg&ved=0CD8Q6AEwAw#v=onepage&q=leveraging%20sales%20by%20%20social%20media&f=false> accessed on 22nd May 2013.
2. The social tradeshow, Leveraging social media & virtual events to connect with your customers,by traci Browne, June 2012, page accessed on 22nd May 2013. http://books.google.co.in/books?id=45ou7SFCB8UC&printsec=frontcover&dq=leveraging+sales+by++social+media&hl=en&sa=X&ei=qc-cUcypF8_LrQfLwIHgBg&ved=0CC4Q6AEwAA
3. Mr.Axel Schultze ina blog post entitled “what is social selling” in 23rd October 2009.
4. Facebook features available at< <http://www.johnhaydon.com/2010/06/facebook-page-features-make-your-day/>>, accessed on 22nd May 2013.
5. Maximizing Linked in for sales & social media marketing by Neal Schaffer , available at <http://books.google.co.in/books?id=2KhZvXGzjgC&printsec=frontcover&dq=leveraging+sales+by++social+media&hl=en&sa=X&ei=qc-cUcypF8_LrQfLwIHgBg&ved=0CDkQ6AEwAg>, accessed on 22nd may 2013,
6. Facebook Marketing: Leveraging Facebook’s features for your marketing campaigns by Brian Carter & Justin Levy , 3rd edition, available at <http://books.google.co.in/books?id=D8ryhTPgJzYC&printsec=frontcover&dq=leveraging+sales+by++social+media&hl=en&sa=X&ei=qc-cUcypF8_LrQfLwIHgBg&ved=0CGMQ6AEwCQ#v=onepage&q=leveraging%20sales%20by%20%20social%20media&f=false> accessed on 22nd May 2013.
7. Twitter company statistics, available at < <http://www.statisticbrain.com/twitter-statistics/>> , accessed on 7th May 2013.
8. Facebook statistics, available at< <http://www.statisticbrain.com/facebook-statistics/>>, accessed on 18th May 2013.
9. percents of people who use social networks, available at< <http://www.statisticbrain.com/social-networking-statistics/>>, accessed on 21st November 2012
10. How has Linkedin Helped, available on <<http://theundercoverrecruiter.com/infographic-linkedin-user-statistics-network-profiles-groups-applications/>> accessed on 7th May 2013.
11. Social Media in 2013: User Demographics For Twitter, Facebook, Pinterest and Instagram, available at < <http://blog.bufferapp.com/social-media-in-2013-user-demographics-for-twitter-facebook-pinterest-and-instagram>> accessed on 10th October 2016.